

@AcademicChatter, #AcademicMentalHealth and Twitter

Workshop/hands-on practices for enhancing researcher mental health and well-being

Fatma Guneri¹, Darragh McCashin², Gokce Gokalp³ and Maria Paola Jimenez⁴

1 Hemisf4ire Design School, Université Catholique de Lille, France

2 Dublin City University, Ireland

3 Middle East Technical University, Ankara, Turkey

4 Universidad del Magdalena, Colombia

Introduction

Twitter has become a ubiquitous platform for people to connect and share information. In academia, Twitter has become a hugely popular online space for academic communities. For example, several prominent accounts such as @AcademicChatter, @PhdVoice, and @happy researchers have used Twitter to promote topical discussion on the link between academia and mental health. Moreover, such accounts carefully employ pertinent hashtags to convey noteworthy topics of interest, notably #AcademicMentalHealth. As such, there is an emerging interest in utilising such data to understand the nuances of academic mental health, and to attain more ecologically valid insights. This project uses the lens of social exchange theory to further explore the online academic discourse on Twitter, with the aim of developing best practice guidelines for researchers to effectively engage with such communities.

Background

Earlier research on the usefulness of Twitter in the academic world has shown that use of Twitter has helped scholar with strengthening existing relationships and building new ones in their research area (Gruzd, Wellman, & Takhteyev, 2011) among other positive benefits such as encouraging institutional innovation (Weller, 2012), indicating the potential of Twitter for building academic communities. In our study in 2022¹ we found that @AcademicChatter is the most popular twitter page among researchers. The tweets come out from Academic Chatter are about the topics such as mental health Phd (connected to tweets from Phdchat, PhdVoice; PhdLife and Monday motivation); resilience&leavingacademiaparadoxes, tweets from Academic Twitter (connected to the tweets from academic jobs and phdchat); tools and methods (Python, econometrics, javascript, webdev); intersectionality (Women who code; gender, activists) and finally education & training (course design, learning management). A similar study where various themes derivated from tweets were done in 2017 (Berry, et al., 2017). Our study will be a contribution to identify the emerging themes since 2022.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7594967>

TWEETS OVER TIME

HASHTAG CLOUD

References

Berry, N., Lobban, F., Belousov, M., Emsley, R., Nenadic, G., & Bucci, S. (2017, 04 05). #WhyWeTweetMH: Understanding Why People Use Twitter to Discuss Mental Health Problems. *JMIR Publications*, 19(4). doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.6173>

Gruzd, A., Wellman, B., & Takhteyev, Y. (2011). Imagining twitter as an imagined community. *American Behavioural Scientist*, 55(10), 1294–1318.

Weller, M. (2011). *The digital scholar: How technology is transforming scholarly practice*. London, UK: Bloomsbury Academic.